

Advanced Metasurfaces for Next-Generation Wireless Communication Networks

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During the past few years, reconfigurable metasurfaces emerged from proof-of-concept theories to practical demonstrations in dynamic and complex electromagnetic environments [1]–[10]. Electromagnetic metasurfaces consist of sub-wavelength passive reconfigurable scatterers, and they are capable of shaping scattered wavefronts at will. It is projected that metasurfaces can be deployed within next-generation wireless networks. Multiple functionalities, such as anomalous reflection and angle-of-arrival sensing, can be achieved using a single adaptable scattering metasurface [8]–[10]. This capability enables integrated sensing and communication, along with user interactions, facilitating end-to-end design and optimization of complex wireless networks.

Recent advancements in metasurface technology have facilitated their seamless integration into wireless communication systems. Building on these developments, we have proposed an arithmetic optimization method based on array antenna scattering synthesis to design periodic reflectors. These reflectors consist of reactively loaded patch elements within a supercell structure. To extend this methodology to practical implementations, we have adapted it for large but finite antenna arrays, achieving uniformly high anomalous reflection efficiencies. Our approach relies on a global scattering synthesis strategy, enabling precise beam deflection and accelerating the optimization of both finite aperiodic and infinite periodic arrays by accurately predicting their scattering behavior [2], [3]. Beyond beam steering, our framework enhances metasurface functionality by enabling precise detection of unknown incident angles of arrival from arbitrary illuminating waves. This dual capability allows metasurfaces to function as simultaneous sensing and reflecting elements, eliminating the need for extensive RF chains, pre-computed data, or expensive real-time measurements [6], [10]. Effectively, in this scenario the metasurface itself acts as a network sensor, offering significant potential for next-generation wireless applications. Furthermore, we integrate metasurface models into network planning tools by bridging electromagnetic principles with communication system characteristics. By passing a limited set of macroscopic electromagnetic parameters from the metasurface design phase to network simulators, we ensure an accurate representation of electromagnetic behavior in large-scale wireless networks [4], [5]. This approach provides reliable system performance estimations while reducing the need for extensive real-world measurements, thus streamlining the design and

deployment of advanced wireless networks.

In this talk, we will discuss some of our smart array designs of advanced metasurfaces that seamlessly integrate with existing conventional antennas. Reconfigurable metasurfaces can automatically scan the electromagnetic spectrum and detect the angular regions for incoming signals, before self-adjusting the scattering pattern through real-time control of the scattering characteristics. These electromagnetics-consistent metasurface models are integrated into wireless network simulators to construct an intelligent radio environment. During the talk, we will pay specific attention to our recent developments in synthesizing such devices and discuss the opportunities for next-generation wireless communication networks.

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